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Investigation Of Causes Of Building Collapse In Nigeria: A Case Of Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

Incessant cases of building failures and collapse in Nigeria is getting more worrisome. This research employs geotechnical and civil engineering test methods in screening the materials and subsoil of six (6) collapsed buildings in Anambra state, southeastern Nigeria in order to determine the causes of their collapse. These tests include borehole-drilling, Cone Penetration Test (CPT), sieve analysis, bulk density, specific gravity; coring, curing and crushing of concrete and masonry block samples. The tests aided in determining the general subsoil conditions of the six collapsed building sites in connection with the foundation state; analyzing the structural elements and the adequacy of the dimensions as well as the quality of the reinforcement bars; determining the integrity and stability of the major structural elements with respect to standards, and detecting the immediate causes of the collapse incidents. Test results' analyses revealed the leading causes of building collapse in the state as unsuitable building materials (45%) and unsuitable foundation (31%). Inappropriate execution (15%) and inappropriate planning (12%) are other causes of building collapse.

Keywords: Building collapse, geotechnical, subsoil, concrete, steel reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Buildings are structures, which serve as shelters for man, his properties and activities and they must be safe for the occupants. Collapse of building either total or partial which could affect all or some of its component leads to the failure of building to perform its intended functions of protection, safety or stability. Building collapse is an extreme case of building failure. It means the superstructure crashes down totally or partially (Olagunyi, et al, 2013; Arilesere, 2002). To obtain the desired satisfaction, buildings must be properly designed, well planned, constructed and maintained (Umeora, 2013; Odulami, 2002).

The common causes of building collapse in Nigeria have been traced to bad design; faulty construction; faulty building materials; foundation failure; extraordinary loads, use of unqualified contractors and poor project monitoring and above all, lack of enforcement of building codes by the relevant Town Planning Officials (Usman et al., 2010; Badejo, 2009; Falobi, 2009; Bamidele, 2000).

Incidents of building collapse in Nigeria are rising annually with Anambra, Lagos, Rivers and Delta states being among the most affected. Anambra State has recorded great damages to human lives and properties as a result of building collapse in recent years (see Table 1). This study is aimed at identifying the causes of collapse of six buildings from the most affected Local Government Areas (LGAs) of the state. From Table 1, it is observed that Orumba North LGA (Oko and Amaokpala) experienced the highest number of collapse buildings followed by Awka South (Awka city & environs), Idemili North (Obosi and Ogidi), Anaocha (Adazi- ani & Adazi-nnukwu) and Aguata (Ekwulobia) LGAs hence one collapsed building site at least from these LGAs was investigated (Table 2).

Table 1: List of collapsed buildings in Anambra State from October 2014 to October 2018

S/N	Date of collapse	Site Location	LGA	Number of floors/stage of work	Casualties
1	2014	No 10 Udi Obanye Street Fegge Onitsha	Onitsha South	6	NG
2	2/6/2014	St. Andrew's Anglican Church Odoakpu Onitsha	Onitsha North	5/ ongoing	4died
3	5/7/2014	No. 8 Alloy Offia Street, Mgbuka Nkpor Onitsha	Onitsha North	5	NG
4 ●	5/10/2014	Ezi-ora village, luxury apartment Adazi-ani	Anaocha	4	1died 20injured
5 ●	27/07/2015	Owelle Aja, Obosi	Idemili North	5	NG
6	27/07/2015	No. 1 Chief Charles Ezeoke street, off Abakiliki street, Awka	Awka South	4/ roofed	3died
7	10/08/2015	Close to Obosi erosion site	Idemili North	NG	NG
8 ●	August, 2015	Standard Plaza Unizik Temporary Site, Enugu-Onitsha Expressway Awka	Awka South	4	Nil
9 ●	22/05/2016	Permanent Site Federal Polytechnic, Oko	Orumba North	4/ 3 rd floor slab	7trapped
10	28/05/2016	Close to Wonderland Hostel, Amawa Amaokpala.	Orumba North	4/ 3 rd floor lintel	NG
11 ●	31/05/16	Near Eke Market, Agba Ekwulobia	Aguata	3 / rendering	3died,5injured
12	07/06/2016	Amaokpala (partial collapse)	Orumba North	4/3 rd floor lintel	Nil
13	June, 2016	Adazi-nnukwu	Anaocha		
14	13/07/2016	Okeleuche layout Ikenga Ndiagu Ogidi	Idemili North	2/ ongoing	3died 3injured
15	30/07/2016	Agbani village behind second market, Ifite Awka	Awka South	NG	NG
16	04/08/2016	Oko	Orumba North	NG	NG
17	2016	Tetfund-sponsored building at Federal Polytechnic, Oko	Orumba North	NG	NG
18	Jan. 2017	Ihengwu village, Oko	Orumba North	4/ ongoing	NG
19	25/03/2017	Along Ogidi-Abatete Road, Nkwo Eziudo market	Idemili North	3x2/ ongoing	Nil
20	15/06/2017	Behind Eke market, Oke-ani village Oko	Orumba North	ongoing	2died,1injured
21	22/06/2017	Road 15 Udoka Housing Estate, Awka	Awka South	2/ongoing	Nil
22	17/07/2017	St. Augustine Cath. Church, Ichida (partial collapse)	Anaocha	4	NG
23	23/07/2017	Frank Chinweike Str., Owelle Aja, Obosi (partial)	Idemili North	3/ ongoing	Nil
24	17/09/2017	Umuchiana village, Ekwulobia	Aguata	NG	NG
25	Nov. 2017	Orlu – Ihiala road before Ubulu-isiuzo village junction, Ihiala	Ihiala	2/ ongoing	Nil
26	30/11/ 17	Close to Odogwu hostel Amansea	Awka North	4/ ongoing	Nil
27	08/01/2018	Opposite Otuocha local stadium Aguleri	Anambra East	3/ roofing	6trapped
28	04/04/2018	Oba airport land, Oba	Idemili South	3/ongoing	NG

29	April 2018	Beside Master B hotel, Ngene- Amawbia	Awka South	2/ abandoned	Nil
30	14/07/2018	Off Tony Eze Str. Owelle-Aja L/out Obosi	Idemili North	4/ ongoing	Nil
31	24/07/2018	F.N. Nwalusi Str. New Friends Estate Amawbia	Awka south	4/ongoing	Nil
32	29/07/2018	Umuatulu Ifite Ani Village Enugwu-ukwu	Njikoka	NG	Nil
33	30/07/2018	First Market Ifite Village Awka	Awka south	4 / paraplet	Nil
34	04/10/18	Close to Yahoo Junction Ifite Awka	Awka south	4/ finishes	Nil
35	18/10/18	Close to Igwe Orizu Road, Okpuno Otolo	Nnewi North	4/Rendering	11 trapped,2died

● **Research Sites**

Table 2 Collapsed building sites under research

Site Designation	Site Address	Intended number of floors	Building stage at collapse time	Date of collapse
A.	Ezi-ora village, luxury apartment Adazi-Ani.	5	4 th floor	5/10/2014
B.	Owelle Aja, Obosi.	5	Completed	27/07/2015
C1.	Standard Plaza Unizik Temporary Site, Enugu-Onitsha Expressway Awka.	4	Ongoing	August, 2015
C2.	Ifite-Amansea Road,Unizik Perm Site, Awka.	4	Roof paraplet	30/07/2018
D.	Permanent Site Federal Polytechnic, Oko.	4	3 rd floor slab	22/05/2016
E.	Near Eke Market, Agba Ekwulobia.	3	Rendering	June, 2016

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The materials used for the test were obtained in situ at the site of the collapsed buildings. They include soil samples, concrete mass samples, masonry blocks, reinforcement bars. The methods employed in discovering the reasons behind the collapse incidents of the studied sites are discussed below:

Subsoil Investigation: Waltham (2002) noted that site investigation is the meeting point of geologist and civil engineers, the objectives of which is determining the subsoil conditions and its suitability for the proposed project. This involves borehole drilling and Cone Penetrometer Test to respectively determine the soil layers and their bearing capacity.

Geotechnical boreholes (BH) were drilled on the sites of collapsed buildings using a standard shell and auger percussion rig. It was used to drill holes through the sandy and clayey strata. The borehole was lined with both 150 mm or 250 mm diameter steel drilling casings, utilizing the 250 mm diameter casings to a depth of 6 m before changing to the 150 mm diameter until the termination of the hole.

The drilling tools consisted of an open-tube with a non-return flap valve at one end called a shell, for non-cohesive (sandy) strata, and mixed soils. A clay cutter is normally employed to drill through stiff cohesive soils. This is attached to the drilling weight called sinker-bar and subsequently attached to the drilling string. The borehole casings were turned down using chain grips, but sometimes driven down using a special hammer. During drilling operations, disturbed samples were regularly taken at depth interval of 0.75m and whenever changes of soil type were observed. In cohesive soil strata, apart from the usual disturbed samples, relatively undisturbed soil samples were taken using the conventional open tube sampler by driving a 100mm diameter sampler through a total of 450mm length. All data and information so observed during the test were carefully recorded on borehole logs and are summarized in Tables 3(a-f).

Table 3a Subsoil conditions of site A

BH No.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	0.75	Very loose reddish brown silty sand(old fill) with rubbles from collapsed building	0.75	21.0
	0.75	2.25	Firm reddish brown silty sandy lateritic clay	1.50	
	2.25	14.25	Firm to stiff reddish brown silty sandy lateritic clay	12.0	
	14.25	21.0	Reddish brown silty sandy lateritic clay with gravel	6.75	
BH 2	0.0	1.0	Very loose reddish brown silty clayey sand(old fill) with rubbles from collapsed building	1.0	21.0
	1.0	3.0	Soft to firm stiffening reddish brown silty sandy lateritic clay	2.0	
	3.0	18.0	Stiff to hardening reddish brown silty sandy lateritic clay	15.0	
	18.0	21.0	Reddish brown/brown silty sand with occasional gravel	3.0	

Table 3b Subsoil conditions of site B

BH No.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	2.0	Red and brown silty sand	2.0	20.0
	2.0	17.0	Red and brown lateritic clayey silty sand	15.0	
	17.0	20.0	Red and brown silty sand	3.0	

Table 3c Subsoil conditions of site C1

BH No.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	0.2	Top soil	0.2	22.5
	0.2	2.75	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	2.75	
	2.75	4.25	Reddish brown lateritic sandy clay	1.5	
	4.25	6.5	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	2.25	
	6.5	8.75	Reddish brown lateritic sandy silty clay with gravel	2.25	
	8.75	11.75	(mottled) inorganic clay with traces of sand	3.0	
	11.75	14.0	(mottled) inorganic clay	2.25	
	14.0	17.75	(mottled) inorganic clay with traces of sand	3.75	
	17.75	19.25	(mottled) sandy silty clay	1.5	
BH 2	19.25	22.25	(mottled) inorganic clay with traces of sand	3.0	22.0
	0.0	0.2	Top soil	0.2	
	0.2	13.0	Reddish brown lateritic sandy clay	13.0	
	13.0	13.75	(mottled) sandy clay with traces of gravel	0.75	
	13.75	14.5	(mottled) clay	0.75	
	14.5	15.25	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	0.75	
BH 3	15.25	22.0	Dark brown sand	6.75	16.5
	0.0	0.2	Top soil	0.2	
	0.2	10.5	Reddish brown lateritic sandy clay	10.5	
	10.5	13.5	Reddish brown lateritic sandy clay with gravel	3.0	
	13.5	15.75	(mottled) inorganic clay with traces of sand	2.25	
	15.75	16.5	(mottled) inorganic clay	0.75	

Table 3d Subsoil conditions of site C2

BH No.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	3.0	Reddish brown lateritic sandy clay with gravel	3.0	15.0
	3.0	15.0	(mottled) clay with gravel	12.0	
BH 2	0.0	3.0	Reddish brown lateritic clay with gravel	3.0	10.5
	3.0	10.5	(mottled) clay with gravel	7.5	

Table 3e Subsoil conditions of site D

BH No.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	0.2	Top soil, dark brown silty sand with plant matter	0.2	25.5
	2.0	25.5	Reddish brown lateritic sandy silty clay	25.3	
BH 2	0.0	0.2	Top soil, dark brown silty sand with plant matter	0.2	20.0
	2	20.0	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	19.8	

Table 3f Subsoil conditions of site E

BH NO.	Top Stratum (m)	Base Stratum (m)	Description of Stratum	Thickness of Stratum (m)	Total Depth of BH (m)
BH 1	0.0	0.2	Top soil	0.2	20.25
	0.2	4.5	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	4.3	
	4.5	20.25	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	15.75	
BH 2	0.0	0.2	Top soil	0.2	23.0
	0.2	5.75	Reddish brown lateritic sand with traces of clay	5.5	
	5.75	23.0	Reddish brown lateritic clayey sand	17.25	

Cone Penetrometer Tests according to Price (2009), consist of pushing a pointed rod into the ground and measuring resistance to progress, the stronger the ground the greater its resistance to progress. CPTs were carried out using 2.5 tons capacity Dutch Cone Penetrometer Machine. This machine measured the resistance to penetration into soil layers. The sequence of layers was then interpreted from the variations of the cone end resistance with depth. The cone was pushed into the ground for 20 or 25cm by means of attached winch system at a uniform rate of about 20mm per seconds. The resistance to penetration of the cone registered on the pressure gauge connected to the pressure capsule was recorded on each borehole. The tube was then pushed down to the cone and the process described above was repeated. The resistance values of all the study sites with depths penetrated is presented in table 4.

Table 4 Cone Penetration Test results

Depth (m)	Cone Resistance (Kg/cm ²)																			
	Site A (4CPT)				Site B (2CPT)		Site C1 (4CPT)				Site C2 (3CPT)		Site D(4CPT)				Site E (4CPT)			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	1	2	3	4	1	2	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
0.25	40	5	30	30	5	10	15	15	15	15	20	20	5	5	5	5	10	10	10	10
0.5	30	5	30	25	10	10	20	15	20	20	20	20	5	5	5	5	10	10	10	10
0.75	20	5	35	25	10	15	25	25	25	25	20	20	5	5	5	5	10	10	10	10
1.0	20	10	15	15	15	15	30	20	30	30	20	20	10	10	10	10	15	10	15	10
1.25	20	10	15	15	20	15	10	10	10	10	20	20	5	5	5	5	10	10	10	10
1.5	20	15	20	20	25	15	15	10	15	15	20	20	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
1.75	20	20	20	20	30	20	20	15	20	20	20	20	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2.0	20	20	25	15	10	20	25	20	25	25	20	20	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2.25	20	20	15	20	15	20	20	20	20	20	25	25	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
2.5	20	20	20	25	20	20	20	25	20	20	25	25	10	10	10	10	15	15	15	15
2.75	25	25	25	30	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
3.0	25	30	15	25	15	15	30	30	30	30	30	30	10	10	10	10	10	15	10	15
3.25	25	25	20	30	20	30	20	20	20	25	30	30	10	15	15	15	10	15	10	15
3.5	25	30	25	35	25	30	25	25	25	20	30	30	10	15	15	15	15	15	15	15
3.75	30	35	30	35	30	35	20	25	25	25	30	35	10	10	15	15	15	15	15	15
4.0	25	30	25	30	20	25	20	30	-	-	30	-35	10	10	15	15	10	10	10	10
4.25	25	25	25	30	25	25	25	25	-	-			15	15	15	15	10	10	10	10
4.5	30	30	30	35	30	20	30	25	-	-			15	15	15	15	10	10	10	10
4.75	40	35	35	30	35	25	35	-	-	-			20	20	20	20				

5.0	35	35	20	30	25	30							20	25	25	20				
5.25	30	30	25	35	30	-														
5.5	30	35	30	40	35	-														
5.75	35	40	35	40	40	-														
6.0	35	40	25	30	30	-														

Geotechnical Laboratory tests

The laboratory tests carried out on the samples from the boreholes include particle size distribution, Atterberg limits (liquid & plastic), natural moisture contents, density (bulk, dry & particle) and triaxial compression tests. Tables 5(a-f) summarize results of these tests. According to Waltham, T. (2002), collapse potential is highest in soils with dry density < 1.5 Mg/m³ liquid limit < 30% and moisture content < 15%.

Table 5a Summary of laboratory test results on site A

BH NO.	Sample depth(m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical & Hydro-meter Analysis (%)			
						Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kpa)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
BH 1	1.5	17										83	17	-
	2.25	17										78	22	-
	4.5	16	2.12	1.83					75	16				-
	6.0	16	2.03	1.61					90	15				-
	10.5	17										69	31	-
	15.0	15										78	22	-
	21.0	13									23	58	19	-
BH 2	1.5	11	2.11	1.9					60	13				-
	3.0	12	2.05	1.83					95	17				-
	5.25	16										67	33	-
	12.75	12										66	25	-
	16.5	10										75	25	-
	18.0	7										82	18	-

Table 5b Summary of laboratory test results on site B

Sample depth (m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical Analysis (%)			
					Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kpa)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
0.0	13				NON-PLASTIC						76	24	-
2.0	17				26	15	11				77	23	-
2.75	15	2.26	1.42	2.63	17	11	6	33	1		75	25	-
4.25	13				30	16	14				75	25	-
7.25	15												-
9.5	14												-
14.0	14				39	20	19				69	31	-
17.0	13				NON-PLASTIC						78	22	-
18.5	14										78	22	-
20.0	12				NON-PLASTIC						81	10	-

Table 5c Summary of laboratory test results on site C1

BH NO.	Sample depth(m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical Analysis(%)			
						Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kna)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
BH 1	1.25	22				31	15	16				65	35	-
	2.75	19	2.0	1.8	2.64	39	22	17	45	16		61	39	-
	4.25	27				41	23	18				58	42	-
	6.5	27				32	18	14				67	33	-
	8.75	31				52	26	26			7	63	30	-
	11.75	103										16	84	-
	14.0	69				81	60	21				16	84	-
	15.5	70										2	98	-
	17.0	70										2	98	-
	17.75	34										45	55	-
	19.25	52					99	55	44			4	96	-
	20.0	42										18	82	-
21.5	31					72	47	25			30	70	-	
BH 2	1.75	26				35	20	15				54	46	-
	3.25	23	1.94	1.62	2.62	37	23	14	33	4		60	40	-
	4.75	23				38	26	12				56	44	-
	7.0	25												-
	9.25	30												-
	13.0	25									7	49	44	-
	13.75	26					54	26	28			47	53	-
	14.5	20					39	24	15			68	32	-
	15.25	12										80	20	-
	16.75	23										96	4	-
	19.0	24										95	5	-
	21.25	21										96	4	-
BH 3	3.0	22				42	24	18				55	45	-
	4.5	18	2.09	1.77	2.63	42	25	17	117	2		54	46	-
	6.0	21				38	24	14				56	44	-
	7.5	27				39	24	15				56	44	-
	10.5	19				54	26	28			9	54	37	-
	13.5	37				102	44	58				18	82	-
	15.0	29				78	26	52				17	83	-
	15.75	24										33	67	-
	18.0	22										5	96	-
21.75	23										6	94	-	

Table 5d Summary of laboratory test results on site C2

BH NO.	Sample depth(m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical Analysis(%)			
						Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kna)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
BH 1	1.5	17				44	19	25			2	52	46	-
	3.0	18			2.58	54	26	28	22	5	6	62	32	-
	4.5	18				53	28	25			11	43	46	-
	6.0	21				-	-	-			-	-	-	-
	7.5	11				52	27	25			20	43	37	-
	9.0	15				-	-	-			-	-	-	-

	10.5	19				51	27	24			27	39	34	-
BH 2	1.0	15				51	28	15			-	54	49	-
	2.5	22				-	-	14			24	60	24	-
	4.0	62				55	28	12			19	56	40	-
	5.5	30				-	-				-	-	-	-
	7.0	19				51	27				9		26	-
	8.5	21				-	-				-	49	-	-
	10.0	14				53	26	28			62	47	14	-

Table 5e Summary of laboratory test results on site D

BH NO.	Sample depth(m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical & Hydrometer Analysis (%)			
						Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kpa)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
BH 1	2.25	12												
	3.0	12				32	22	17				76	24	-
	3.75	11	2.18	1.94	2.62	32	23	18	50	8		74	26	-
	6.75	25				35	18	14				71	29	-
	9.0	29												-
	12.0	27				34	19	15				70	30	-
	15.0	22												-
	18.0	24				34	18	16				71	29	-
	20.25	27				34	18	16				68	32	-
	23.25	21				31	16	15				69	31	-
24.75	21										68	32	-	
BH 2	2.0	18												-
	6.5	13	2.13	1.86	2.63	45	25	20				69	31	-
	7.25	23				46	22	24				70	30	-
	10.25	23				47	23	24				69	31	-
	16.25	25				49	26	23				69	31	-

Table 5f Summary of laboratory test results on site E

BH NO.	Sample depth(m)	Moisture Content (%)	Bulk Density (Mg/m ³)	Dry Density (Mg/m ³)	Particle Density (Mg/m ³)	Atterberg limits			Triaxial test		Mechanical & Analysis (%)			
						Liquid Limit	Plastic Limit	Plastic Index	Undrained Cohesion (kpa)	Ø	Gravel	Sand	Silt	Clay
BH1	3.0	21			2.62	28	16	12						-
	3.75	22			2.61	28	17	11				68	32	-
	4.5	28			2.60	37	20	17				64	36	-
	8.25	30				38	23	15				66	34	-
	12.75	33				37	22	15				65	35	-
	18.0	33				38	21	17				63	37	-
	20.25	31				37	21	16				63	37	-
												62	38	-
BH 2	2.75	28				22	13	9				72	28	-
	3.5	29												-
	5.75	25			2.62	34	18	16				66	34	-
	6.5	29			2.63	35	17	18				64	36	-

8.0	31				31	17	14				66	34	-
11.75	27												
15.5	30										61	39	
21.5	28										62	38	

Determination of the compressive strength of concrete & sandcrete block samples.

Compressive strength tests were carried on randomly handpicked samples of concrete mass. Coring was done on the concrete specimen with a 50mm diamond bit coring machine after which they were cured for 24 hours before being subjected to compression test by crushing with a 300KN capacity compression machine. These tests were done on samples from sites A, B, C2, D, and E as the collapse debris had been cleared from site C1 before the investigation. Additionally, compression test was carried on randomly handpicked (used & about to be used) sandcrete blocks from sites D & E only. Tables 6 presents the compressive strengths of the concrete samples and different types and sizes of sandcrete blocks tested.

Table 6: Results of concrete and sandcrete compressive strength tests.

Sample	Compressive strength (N/mm ²) of concrete samples							Remarks
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	
Site A	16.03	18.49	17.16	16.79	20.07	16.66	19.75	Not satisfactory
Site B	3.6	2.7	2.6	2.5	1.9	2.2	-	Not satisfactory
Site C1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Not Tested
Site C2	5.3	5.2	5.4	4.2	5.6	4.7	-	Not satisfactory
Site D	1.4	1.4	1.5	2.2	2.6	3.1	2.4	Not satisfactory
Site E	0.6	1.1	0.7	-	-	-	-	Not satisfactory
Compressive strength (N/mm²) of sandcrete samples								
		Solid blocks					Hollow blocks	
		SB1	SB2	SB3		HB1		
Site D		0.3	0.4	0.4		0.2	Not satisfactory	
semi-hollow sandcrete blocks								
Site E		0.4			0.5			Not satisfactory

Determination of the yield stress of steel reinforcement

Twisted reinforcement bars were randomly handpicked from the collapse sites under study except for Awka sites where debris had been cleared before this research. Tensile tests were carried on straightened reinforcement bars after being hand sawn to 320mm length in accordance to NIS: 117: 2004, yield stress values of $\geq 410\text{N/mm}^2$ and ductility/ elongation of $\geq 12\%$. This provided information on the ductility of the reinforcement bars under uniaxial tensile stress and the obtained data include yield strength and percentage elongation (Tables 7a & 7b).

Table 7a Tensile test results on steel reinforcement (Yield Stress)

Bar size	Mean Yield Stress (N/mm ²)					
	Site A	Site B	Site C1	Site C2	Site D	Site E
8mm	358.91	399.12	-	-	-	419.35
10mm	376.58	349.89	-	-	-	-
12mm	367.77	318.16	-	431.27	284.43	418.44
16mm	362.38	397.01	-	425.68	303.76	435.87
20mm	408.91	-	-	-	-	-
25mm	-	477.28	-	-	-	-
Remark	Not satisfactory	Not satisfactory	Not tested	Satisfactory	Not satisfactory	Satisfactory

Table 7b Tensile test results on steel reinforcement (Elongation)

Bar size	Mean Elongation (%)					
	Site A	Site B	Site C1	Site C2	Site D	Site E
8mm	7.75	4.67	-	-	-	12.38
10mm	7.73	16.05	-	-	-	-
12mm	12.63	13.26	-	11.36	12.51	6.03
16mm	11.56	9.93	-	11.34	15.73	11.20
20mm	12.49	-	-	-	-	-
25mm	-	14.15	-	-	-	-
Remarks	12mm & 20mm- Satisfactory, others not satisfactory	Satisfactory(10m m & 12mm) Others- Not satisfactory	Not tested	Not satisfactory	Satisfactory	Satisfactory(8 mm) Others- Not satisfactory

Framed Structure Analysis: This checks if a building was well structurally framed to bear the expected loads. Framed structures according to Bazant (1966) are systems of bars with rigid joints. Framed structure is made up of columns, beams, slabs and load bearing walls, all connected to one another to resist lateral and gravity load (deformation) and overcome large moments of applied loading. The columns are anchored in a foundation for overall stability of the structure. The ability of the frame to continue supporting vertical loads depends on both the capacity of the framing system to transfer these loads to adjacent components and the capacity of the components to support the additional loads. If one or both conditions become(s) deficient, progressive failure and subsequent collapse will result. In this research, framed structures were analyzed for sites C2, D & E only based on investigations of samples collected, laboratory tests, visual observations and relevant discussions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site A

Visual observation reveals that the topography of the built area has a gentle slope and the foundation (pad) with depth of 1.5m was met in a collapsed state.

The subsoil is predominantly silty sandy lateritic clay and the sand is mainly medium to fine grained. The liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index range from 23% - 37%, 13% - 19% and 10% - 18% respectively. The subsoil has a low natural moisture content varying from 7% to 17%. From the triaxial compressive test, the subsoil cohesion ranges from 60 – 95KN/m²; angle of internal friction 13° -17° and bulk density 2.03 - 2.12 Mg/m².

The tensile strength test carried on the reinforcement bars shows the yield strength did not meet standard value of 460N/mm² according to BS4449:1998. The compressive test results show that the concrete compressive strength values are far less than the required standard value of 25N/mm². The poor quality reinforcement bars and the poor concrete mix could be some of the errors in construction procedures that compromised the integrity of the building.

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site B

Visual observation reveals that the built area and environs was swampy or water-lodged and the building premises lacked storm water drain network.

The subsoil is mainly red and brown lateritic clayey silty sand and silty sand. The liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index range from 17% - 39%, 11% - 20% and 6% - 19% respectively. The subsoil has a moderate natural moisture content varying from 12% to 17%. From the triaxial compressive test, the subsoil cohesion value was 31KN/m²; angle of internal friction 1° and bulk density 2.26 Mg/m².

The tensile strength test carried on the reinforcement bars shows the yield strength did not meet standard value of 460N/mm² according to BS4449:1998. The compressive test results show that the concrete compressive strength values are far less than the required standard value of 25N/mm². The poor quality reinforcement bars and the poor concrete mix could be parts of the errors in construction procedures that led to the collapse of the building.

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site C1

Visual observations suggest poor building materials and inappropriate foundations. Also the expansive nature of the soils and fluctuating water levels due to changes in climatic conditions contributed to the total failure of the structure.

The samples taken from boreholes are sandy clay, clayey sand, sandy silty clay and dark and brown sand. The CPT readings show that the subsoil is generally soft. Sieve analysis on the sand shows that it falls within the grading zone 3 and is predominantly fine to medium grain size which is poor for concreting (fine aggregates that falls within grading zone 2 are considered good for concreting).

The liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index range from 31% - 102%, 15% - 60% and 12% - 58% respectively. The subsoil has natural moisture content varying from 12% to 103% which shows the materials are of high moisture content. From the triaxial compressive test, the subsoil cohesion ranges from 45 – 117KN/m²; angle of internal friction 2° -16° and bulky density 2.0 - 2.05 Mg/m². The particle density of the sand gives an unsatisfactory result of 2.62 – 2.64Mg/m³ which is not within required specification. All these point to soft or weak subsoil.

No information is gathered concerning the compressive strength of the concrete and sandcrete blocks as well as of the reinforcements bars used in construction of the collapsed site because majority of the debris had been removed at the time of this research.

The weak nature and the high plasticity of the subsoil is a probable cause of the building collapse.

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site C2

The liquid limit, plastic limit and plasticity index range from 44% - 54%, 19% - 26% and 10% - 18% respectively. The subsoil has a low natural moisture content varying from 23% to 28%. From the triaxial compressive test, the subsoil cohesion is 22KN/m² and angle of internal friction 5°. The subsoil strata encountered while carrying out the boring and Cone Penetration Test comprise of Reddish Brown Lateritic Sandy Clay with gravel, which indicates a very stable bearing capacity for the soil. Hence, it can be inferred that the bearing capacity of the investigated soil was adequate for the imposed load and could not have been a cause of the collapse. Therefore, lack of geotechnical investigation for appropriate foundation design points to foundation failure resulting from improper foundation design as one probable cause of the collapse.

The compressive strength results of the tested cored concrete samples ranged from 4.2 N/mm² to 5.6 N/mm² and were remarked extremely not satisfactory.

This emphatically shows that the concrete compressive strength values are far less than the required standard value of 25 N/mm² for the structural elements of this number of floors. Thus, it could be inferred that the concrete mix quality was less than the expected standard and this could be one of the major errors in construction procedure that may have compromised the integrity of the building. In addition, the structural frame of the building may have been adversely affected since the integrity of the concrete works was highly compromised. The tensile stress test conducted on the high yield concrete reinforcement bars samples (sizes of 12 mm & 16 mm) shows that all the reinforcement bars with the values (425.68 N/mm² – 431.27 N/mm²) are above the accepted standard Yield stress values of 410 N/mm² and ductility of 12% and above in accordance to NIS: 117:2004. Thus, it could be inferred that the yield stress of the tested concrete reinforcement bar samples was of expected standard and this could not be one of the errors in construction procedure that may have compromised the integrity of the building. Therefore, poor quality concrete mix, wrong foundation and poor workmanship are probable causes of the collapse.

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site D

The samples taken from boreholes are sandy silty clay and clayey sand and the CPT readings show that the subsoil is generally soft. Sieve analysis on the sand shows that it falls within the grading zone 3 and is predominantly fine to medium grain size which is poor for concreting. The value of the bulk density is 1.46 Mg/m³ and it falls below the required specification of 1.7 Mg/m³ – 1.8 Mg/m³ for fine aggregates. The particle density of the sand gives an unsatisfactory result of 2.59Mg/m³ which is not within required specification. Coarse aggregate between 75mm and 150mm was used for concreting and this is beyond required specification for appropriate concreting.

Visually, foundations were on individual footings which were resting directly on the floor without adequate concrete screeding and the building load was carried by the columns. The building lacked decking beams causing the suspended slabs to rest directly on weak sandcrete block walls as there were no beams or girders to help transmit floor loads to the columns. The internal partitioning acted as load bearing walls and the load bearing walls were grossly inadequate in compressive strength.

The reinforcement bars and the stirrups used on the columns were inadequately sized and the stirrups were widely spaced on the reinforcement bars. The concrete compressive strength values from the tested cored concrete were far below the threshold value of 25 N/mm².

The primary cause of the collapse is the loss of vertical load carrying capacity in critical building components which led to the total vertical collapse. Inadequate foundation on expansive subsoil under water-saturated conditions and the use of poor quality building materials are other critical factors that contributed to the collapse.

Discussion on Probable Causes of the collapse at Site E

The collapsed building according to information gathered was not approved by the relevant authorities, was being supervised by a non-building professional and was constructed within a relatively short period of time. It was also built on a flood plain.

The samples taken from boreholes are sandy silty clay and clayey sand. The CPT readings show that the subsoil is generally soft and consequently the bearing capacity of the soil was inadequate for the imposed load and this is one of the probable causes of the collapse.

Though the reinforcement bars were of expected yield stress but the 12mm and 16mm samples failed in ductility and ductility of reinforcement bars help to withstand crack propagation. It was also observed that the structural elements were inadequately reinforced to safely accommodate the transmittable loads of the structure, the stirrups inadequately spaced and that 12mm reinforcement bars were predominantly used. The concrete compressive strength values from the tested concrete mass samples and sandcrete block samples were far below the threshold values of 25 N/mm² and 1.5 N/mm² respectively. These are errors in construction procedures that might have led to the building collapse.

Poor foundation type on a changing sub-grade condition and water movements as well as the expansive subsoil are all contributing factors to the collapse.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been ascertained from this study that collapse of any building is caused by multiple factors. From the physical observations and analysis of tests conducted on each of the collapse sites, the adjudged causes are summarized in Table 9 below.

Table 9: Identified Causes of Building Collapse for the Investigated Sites.

Identified Causes	Sites Affected	Grouping of the causes	%
Sloppy Topography	A	Inappropriate Planning	12
Water-logged / Swampy Terrain	B		
Built on flood plain	E		
Weak Subsoil /Overloading	C1, D, E	Unsuitable Foundation	31
Foundation Errors	A, C1, C2, D, E		
Poor Concrete Mix	A, B, C2, D, E	Unsuitable Materials	42
Poor Sandcrete/Masonry Block Mix	D, E		
Inadequate Reinforcement	A, B, D, E.		
Inadequate Frame Structure	D, E	Inappropriate Execution	15
Non-professional supervision/Poor workmanship	C2, E		

RECOMMENDATION

Considering the analyses of the results of the tests conducted on the collapse sites, the following recommendations are deemed fit:

- ✓ Relevant authorities should enact and enforce laws guiding construction services. Registered builders should be employed to enforce the enacted building regulations.
- ✓ Only professionals in building construction should be allowed to participate in construction of buildings from start to finish.
- ✓ Compulsory checks on the materials to be used for buildings should be made on building sites by quality control firms. This is to ensure their compliance with the British Standard.
- ✓ Government should reduce the cost of building materials, in order to discourage use of substandard materials. Importation of these materials should also be monitored to ensure only materials of good standards are brought into the country.
- ✓ Subsoil investigation on proposed building sites should be enforced especially for multi-storey buildings. This helps to ascertain the nature, capacity of the subsoils and the suitable foundation.
- ✓ Periodic building maintenance culture should be imbibed to increase the service life of buildings.

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